

A Social Marketing Approach to Safer Driving in Nigeria

Habibu Ahmed Sharif¹, Murtala Ibrahim¹, Julius T. Ndaghu¹ and Dahiru Mohammed Yole²

1 Department of Management Technology, Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola, Nigeria

2 Department of Banking and Finance, Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola, Nigeria

Abstract: Due to increased urbanisation and motorisation, the road transport sector has become instrumental in the development of the world economy. However, this has left the society and the environment with negative impacts, otherwise refer to as negative externalities. One of the most obvious evidence of these external costs is the road traffic accidents (RTAs). RTAs have physical, social, emotional and economic implications. To address these implications, the international community has responded with series of programmes and policies. However, RTAs have continue to claim the lives and property of people of especially developing countries who, unlike their developed counterparts, have not been successful in implementing programmes and policies that drastically reduce the prevalence of RTAs. In this study, we highlighted the importance of social marketing in addressing the lingering problems of RTAs in Nigeria. We provided some practical examples on how marketing concepts could be applied in addressing the social aspect of these issues and maintain safer driving. We believe that social marketing will be (and remains) the only option to overcoming RTAs and their attendant health, economic, environmental and social challenges in, especially, developing countries where RTAs are a major problem.

Keywords: Social Marketing, Road Traffic Accidents, Safer Driving, Nigeria

I. Introduction

In recent years, the transport sector has grown tremendously with the road transport being the major mover of this growth (European Commission, 2012). This is due to increased number of vehicles on the world's roads. Between 2013 and 2015, there was about 16% increase in the number of vehicles on the world's roads, and in 2014 alone, a record of 67 million passenger cars came into circulation (WHO, 2015). This has led to positive impacts on the economy, but negative impacts on the environment and the society. These negative impacts, otherwise refer to as negative externalities, represent external costs that are paid not only by the transport service provider and the customer, but also by the society and the environment (Bonca, Udovc & Rodela, 2017). According to Banfi et al., (2000), the road transport sector contributes a whopping 92 per cent of all transport external costs. One of the most obvious evidence of these external costs is the road traffic accidents (RTAs).

RTAs constitute a significant global public health challenge and are leading causes of deaths and injuries around the globe, in addition to some significant economic consequences (WHO, 2016b). It is estimated that about 1.3 million people die to road traffic crashes every year and has become a leading cause of deaths for young people aged 15-29 years (United Nations, 2016; WHO, 2015). Apart from the burden of mortality resulting road traffic crashes, about 20-50m people suffer from road traffic injuries each year, with many sustaining lifelong disabilities (United Nations, 2010; WHO, 2011; United Nations, 2016). And while only about 48 per cent of world registered vehicles are registered in low and middle income countries, over 90 per cent of RTAs occur in these countries (WHO, 2011). Economically, RTAs have been estimated to cause families, victims and countries around 3 per cent of their gross domestic products (WHO 2011; United Nations, 2016; WHO, 2015).

African region continues to have the highest road traffic death rates, while the lowest rates are in the European region, notably among its high income countries, many of which have been very successful in achieving and sustaining reductions in death rates, despite increasing motorisation (WHO, 2015). A quarterly report of the African Development Bank (AfDB) in 2014 revealed that RTAs caused 25% of all injury related deaths in Africa and recorded higher rate of human morbidity than diseases (Palamuleni & David, 2015). However, despite these predictable and preventable challenges, actions to combat RTAs are largely inadequate (WHO, 2015).

RTAs are likely to become the 5th (WHO, 2011) or even the 3rd (Bongardt, Schmid, Huizenga & Litman, 2011) major causes of deaths and injuries by 2030. Without action, RTAs are predicted to result in the deaths of around 1.9m people annually by 2020 (WHO, 2011). Developed countries have over the years succeeded in reducing the rate of fatalities and deaths resulting from RTAs, however, this menace continues to be one of the major challenges in the transport sector of developing countries (Bongardt, Schmid, Huizenga & Litman, 2011). RTAs have physical, social, emotional and economic implications (Atubi & Gbadamosi, 2015). Apart from the deaths resulting from RTAs, accidents take a dominant share of overall external costs of transportation on the society, such as the costs related to medical care for the victims (Bongardt, Schmid, Huizenga & Litman, 2011).

Table 1: Top 10 leading causes of death, 2004 and 2030 compared

	2004	2030
Rank	Disease or injury	Disease or injury
1	Ischaemic heart disease	Ischaemic heart disease
2	Cerebrovascular disease	Cerebrovascular disease
3	Lower respiratory infections	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
4	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Lower respiratory infections
5	Diarrhoeal disease	Road traffic injuries
6	H I V / A I D S	Trachea, bronchus, lung cancers
7	T u b e r c u l o s i s	D i a b e t e s m e l l i t u s
8	Trachea, bronchus, lung cancers	Hypertensive heart disease
9	Road traffic injuries	S t o m a c h c a n c e r
10	Prematurity and low-birth weight	H I V / A I D S

Source: Adapted from WHO (2011)

The social impacts of road traffic deaths and injuries is not limited to the people involved in the crashes, but their impacts are also felt by the families of the victims, their governments, and the society at large. Physical and psychological abnormalities can affect road traffic survivors and their families long after the crash, limiting their work and personal lives activities (WHO, 2016c). Apart from the increasing burden of RTAs on global scale, many household finances are seriously affected. Families suffer a lot of hardship due to the death of the family bread winner from road accident, while many continue with the long standing care of family members that sustained injuries from accidents. Rapid response and regular rehabilitation follow-up will go a long way in addressing the traumatic conditions associated with road traffic fatalities.

Efforts are being made around the globe to address the menace of RTAs. In March 2010, the United Nations General Assembly adopted Resolution 64/255 and officially proclaimed a Decade of Action for Road Safety 2011-2020 (United Nations, 2010). This was sequel to the resolution reached at the First Global Ministerial Conference on Road Safety held in Moscow, Russia in November 2009 (United Nations, 2009; United Nations, 2010; WHO, 2011). The resolution called on Member States to take the necessary steps to make their roads safer, and for WHO to monitor the situation through its Global Status Report on Road Safety series (WHO, 2015). This global plan¹ provides guidelines for the formulation and implementation of road safety policies - both at national and global scale - that could result in stabilising and reducing the forecasted level of road traffic fatalities around the globe (WHO, 2011). If this is achieved, a cumulative total of 5 million lives, 50 million serious injuries and US\$5 trillion could be saved over the decade (WHO, 2011).

In another development, on April 19 2011, the Multilateral Development Banks Road Safety Initiative² was launched by a consortium of seven regional development banks³ to scale up efforts to provide resources for safety projects and the development of road safety management capacity, infrastructure and performance safety measures (United Nations, 2012). In 2010, WHO and five other consortium partners, together with the Bloomberg Philanthropies, initiated a

¹ The global plan was developed by the United Nations Road Safety Collaboration (UNRSC) and stakeholders from around the world. The plan has five main pillars of activities/categories, and indicators to help measure progress in each of the pillars (WHO 2011).

² On 11 November 2009, ahead of the First Global Ministerial Conference on Road Safety in Moscow, seven Multilateral Development Banks issued a joint statement on a shared approach to managing road safety in the context of harmonising policies for road safety operations.

³ The participating banks are the African Development Bank, Asian Development Bank, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, European Investment Bank, Inter-American Development Bank, Islamic Development Bank and the World Bank. In April 2012, the Development Bank of Latin America (CAF) joined the initiative.

program, dubbed RS10 Project, to further road safety in 10 countries of Brazil, Cambodia, China, Egypt, India, Kenya, Mexico, Russia, Turkey and Viet Nam. Efforts are focused on legislation and enforcement and educating the public through social marketing campaigns (WHO, 2011). With increased awareness on the need, and the growing recognition of the contribution of the road safety to health, development and broader environmental objectives as contained in the sustainable development goals of the United Nations, setting a target of halving the number of road traffic deaths by 2020 is a clear action towards achieving this objective (WHO, 2015).

In Nigeria, policies and programs have been developed and implemented with a view to eliminating the menace of RTAs. However, these policies/programs have failed to yield optimum, positive result. This may not be unconnected with the fact that most of these policies do not take into consideration the social dimension of the program. Using Kotler & Zaltman's (1971) social marketing approach, we highlighted the importance of social marketing in addressing the lingering problems of RTAs in Nigeria. We provided some practical examples on how marketing concepts could be applied in addressing the social aspect of these issues. We believe that social marketing will be (and remains) the only option to overcoming RTAs and their attendant health, economic, environmental and social challenges in, especially, developing countries where RTAs are a major problem. In the next section, we present the state of affairs of RTAs in Nigeria, their causes, and some of the policy interventions put in place to overcome them over the years. In section three, the importance of social marketing, using the four marketing Ps, in addressing road safety challenges, is presented. We provided examples of how each of the four marketing Ps could be used to inculcate safer driving habits among motorists and road users in Nigeria. The last section wraps up and concludes the study.

II. Road Traffic Accidents in Nigeria

As at 2013, Nigeria had registered vehicles totalled 5,791,446 made up of 3,267,139 cars and 4-wheeled light vehicles and 2,524,307 motorised 2- and 3-wheels (WHO, 2015). This statistics is not even inclusive of heavy trucks and buses (WHO, 2015). With the worsening deterioration of other modes of transportation, and the inadequacy of the road system - 35 cars per kilometre and a population/road ratio of 861 persons per kilometre of typical Nigerian road - the road system in Nigeria handles about 90 percent of all transport activities (Akpoghomeh, 2012). In years 2016 and 2015, 9,694 and 9,734 RTAs were respectively recorded. Out of these figures 5,053 and 5,440 persons were killed in 2016 and 2015 respectively. The 2016 figure involved a whopping 65,467 people, out of which 30,105 people were injured (FRSC, 2016). These statistics show that on average, five deaths were recorded out of every 10 crashes in Nigeria (FRSC, 2016). Analysis of the RTAs from 1960 to 2016 revealed that a total of 1,125,377 accidents involving 1,559,851 persons were recorded. Number of persons injured were 1,208,890 while those killed were 350,961 persons (FRSC, 2016). Of all the subjects that are involved in road traffic accidents in Nigeria, 29.1 percent suffer disability and 13.5 percent are unable to return to work (Labinjo et al., 2010). According to FRSC (2016), human related factors especially over speeding has over the years been the major cause of RTAs in Nigeria. For example, in 2016 alone, over speeding in particular accounted for about 33.9% of the total crashes (FRSC, 2016). In a bid to curtail the rate of crashes due to speed, the FRSC introduced the compulsory installation and use of speed limit device⁴ in commercial vehicles in Nigeria in 2016, with plans underway to adopt a nationwide application for all motorists in the country (FRSC, 2016).

2.1 Causes of road traffic accidents in Nigeria

Growth in urbanisation and increasing number of motorisation, coupled with the attitudes of most motorists to defy road traffic laws on dilapidated roads, meant that more accidents are recorded on Nigerian roads. The overdependence on the road by commuters in Nigeria for the movement of people and property - considering the fact that Nigeria has no well coordinated public transport system and with moribund rail system that may serve as a reliever to the road transport system - exert a lot of pressure on the already dilapidated roads and this means that more often the roads develop potholes and cracks, which increase the chances of accidents.

Generally, causes of RTAs can be categorised into two major groups: general causes and specific causes (Ansari, Akhdar, Mandoorah & Moutaery, 2000). The general causes of RTAs include increase in number of vehicles and expansion of transport network, large national developmental projects that require the support of existing or additional road networks, and activities of foreigners who have little knowledge of the local transport systems and conditions (Ansari, Akhdar, Mandoorah & Moutaery, 2000). However, it is our view that while increased vehicles and developmental projects have essentially contributed immensely to increased RTAs in Nigeria, foreigners actions towards road transport have little contribution to RTAs in the country. The specific causes include driver error, over-speeding, and poor cognisance of road signs and road conditions (Ansari, Akhdar, Mandoorah & Moutaery, 2000).

⁴ Log on to <http://speedlimiter.frsc.gov.ng> for comprehensive information on speed limit device in Nigeria

Other studies have different classifications of the causes of RTAs in the country (Akpoghomeh, 2012; Adeyemi & Adewole, 2017; Arthur, 2015). For example, Akpoghomeh (2012) categorised the causes of RTAs into three: human factor (including driver error, intoxication, and distraction), technical factor (including route design, vehicle defects, and vehicular faults) and environmental factors (such as bad weather). Akpoghomeh (2011) has also made a distinction between the actual and exacerbating causes of traffic accidents. The remote, contributory, or exacerbating factors are speed of operation, operator's skill and/or impairment, route design and vehicle design. The actual causes, on the other hand, include tiredness and sleep, poor vision, hearing loss/deafness, lack of concentration, driver error, distractions, road design, vehicle defects, poor judgement, lack of attention, and reckless driving (Akpoghomeh, 2011).

Thus, human related factors have been reported the most majorly factors causing RTAs (Adeyemi & Adewole 2017), with over-speeding consistently been identified as the major human factor causing RTAs (Adeyemi & Adewole, 2017; Arthur, 2015; Akpoghomeh, 2012). This is consistent with a report issued by the country's road safety agency, the Federal Road Safety Corps, in 2016 which indicated that speed violation constitutes some 33.9% (or 3,848 cases) of the total factors identified. Other factors include loss of control with 15.4% (1,753 cases); dangerous driving, accounted for 8.5% (or 969 cases); and poor weather, accounting for 0.2% (or 27 cases) of the total identified causes. Thus, according to FRSC (2016), the three identified speed related factors (speed violation, loss of control, and dangerous driving) accounted for 57.8% of the causes of crashes, all of which are related to the inability of the human element to adequately maintain a safer driving behaviour.

As observed since the early 1990s by Asogwa (1992), legislative and other counter measures have been proved ineffective in curtailing the menace of road accidents in Nigeria. A study of 38 countries in May 1984 by the African Technical Review listed Nigeria the number one for road accidents and fatality rates (Asogwa, 1992). Young adults aged 20-34 (Asogwa, 1978) or 15-44 (Adeyemi & Adewole, 2017) years, who are the energetic and working class of the population, accounted for more than half of accident victims (Adeyemi & Adewole, 2017; Asogwa, 1978). The deplorable road accidents in the country is not because of lack of measures to counter them. For example, studies have consistently reported that better roads have resulted in excessive over-speeding and reckless driving, further exacerbating the road accident incidences (Asogwa, 1992; Arthur, 2015; Arno, 2014; Adeyemi & Adewole, 2017).

2.2 Road Safety Policies and Interventions in Nigeria

A number of policies and interventions have been put in place in order to curb the menace of RTAs in Nigeria. However, these policies, though instrumental in some areas, have yet to inculcate safer driving habits among motorists in the country. Oyo State was the first to establish a road traffic agency in Nigeria with the creation of the Oyo State Road Safety Corps (nicknamed 'MAJAMAJA') through Edict 18 of 1977 with the mandates of preventing and minimising road accidents, taking prompt care of victims of road accidents, educating drivers and prospective drivers in the proper use of highways, and conducting research into the causes of motor accidents and methods of prevention. It was reported the MAJAMAJA had succeeded in reducing the rate of traffic injuries in Oyo State from 1978 to 1981 before it was banned by the then Federal Government from operating in federal roads in the state following a political feuds between the then UPN government in Oyo State and the then Federal government controlled by the NPN (Atubi & Gbadamosi, 2015).

In 1988, the Federal government established the Federal Road Safety Commission under Decree 45 of 1988, initially mandated to operate only in federal highways in the country but later expanded to cover all roads in Nigeria through an amendment Decree 35 of August 1992 (Atubi & Gbadamosi, 2015). The Commission has the following functions:

- i. To prevent and minimise accidents on the highways;
- ii. To Clear obstructions on any part of the highways;
- iii. To educate drivers, motorist and other members of the public generally on the proper use of the highways;
- iv. To give prompt attention and care to victims of accidents;
- v. To conduct research into the causes of RTAs and methods of preventing them;
- vi. To determine and enforce speed limits for all categories of roads and vehicles.

III. Social Marketing

In its prime form, social marketing is the application of marketing tools to foster behavioural change and achieve a social objective (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971). Such behavioural change could be in the form of public health challenges and injury prevention (Smith, 2006), environmental protection (Maibach, 1993), or transportation system (McGovern, 2005). It may sometimes be in the form of discouraging a particular set of behaviours or some specific, undesirable actions - a 'negabehaviour' concept proposed by Ross and Tomlinson (2011). A negabehaviour is a "manner of conducting oneself that supplants undesirable actions—that is, the behavior of not performing specific, undesirable actions" (Ross & Tomlinson, 2011 p. 1). Social marketing is also targeted at population-wide behavioural change, not individual

(Lefebvre, 2011). However, since it is the individuals that make up the population, individual behavioural change is an integral component of the success of the social marketing campaigns. Behavioural change is an incremental process that begins with people current realities, and successively applied to guide ones way of life (Lefebvre, 2011).

The application of social marketing has passed through various stages and has taken different shapes. Lefebvre & Flora (1988), Hastings & Haywood (1991) and Hastings & Haywood (1994) gave social marketing widespread exposure in the public health field, providing bases for debating on its application and contribution. The international community has also recognised the importance of social marketing in ensuring safer driving behaviour. The dubbed RS10 Project, largely supported by WHO and the Bloomberg Philanthropies, aims to use social marketing concepts to further road safety in 10 countries (WHO, 2011). However, social marketing application in especially the road transport system, has not received much attention by the literature.

This study therefore looks at how social marketing concepts could be applied to address the road transport challenges facing Nigeria. The aim is to instil safer driving habits among motorists and the general public. For example, it is observed that wearing a seat belt while driving reduces the risk of serious, fatal injury by between 40-65% while wearing a motorcycle helmet reduces the risk of death by 40% and reduces the risk of serious head injuries by 70% (United Nations, 2010). But how can these be made to be accepted by the target customers and how can the target customers be influenced to adopt these habits? This is a challenge for the social marketer. In the next section, we make a presentation of the four Ps of marketing and how each could contribute to the social marketing campaigns of safer driving in Nigeria.

3.1 The Four Marketing Ps

Kotler & Zaltman (1971) built their discussions and analyses of social marketing on the four P's of marketing that form the marketing mix proposed by McCarthy in 1968. This idea stressed that marketing is all about developing the right product backed by the right promotion and put in the right place at the right price (Perreault & McCarthy, 2002; Kotler & Zaltman, 1971). All the 4Ps in the marketing tool are needed in order to deliver the desired product and service to the target audience that would result in the desired behavioural change (Lee & Kotler, 2009). These marketing elements form the backbone for the planning and implementation of any marketing strategy (Lefebvre & Flora, 1988). We shall discuss each of these elements and highlight their applicability to social marketing and road transportation programs.

3.1.1 Product: Traditionally, marketers try to understand the needs and wants of their target market and attempt to design products and services that meet their desires which, if well designed, available and affordable, the product would be bought (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971). One of the major challenges faced by social marketers is designing a program that market a product that is essentially intangible. As a common knowledge, a product is typically conceived as something tangible that can be exchanged with a target market (Lefebvre & Flora, 1988). The product in road transport is safer driving, but how does a driver buys a "safer driving" idea? According to Lefebvre and Flora (1988), the challenge is to begin to make these "intangibles" tangible in a way that appeals to the target audience. Here various products are to be designed to make partial contribution to the social objectives, bearing in mind the core product - safer driving (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971). According to Kotler & Zaltman (1971 p. 7), "the social marketer remains aware of the core product (safer driving) and tries to create various tangible products and services which are buyable and which advance the social objective." This may involve the creation of consumer market where products and services (such as the importance of enrolling in a driving school to know about road traffic signs, rules, regulations and offenses and to obtain a driving licence; installation of speed limiting device, the importance of wearing seat belts while driving, stop driving and eating campaign, stop driving and calling campaign, radio and TV shows on the dangers of reckless driving, market shows, periodic discussions/debates on safer driving in schools and universities, road traffic curricula in schools and universities, home visits to motorists to discuss road safety issues - this will give a sense of belonging to the motorists that the agency is actually committed to safer drives, print pieces such as newspaper columns; billboard messages; flyers; stickers; and posters) that promotes safer driving are obtained. Thus, the social agency must be innovative enough to offer new range of products and services and must be able to motivate purchases for both the old and the new products and services.

3.1.2 Price: Social marketing has an expanded view of price beyond the monetary aspect to include behavioural, psychological, social, temporal, structural, geographical and physical reasons that stimulate or place barriers on the customer to either engage in exchange or decline (Lefebvre & Flora, 1988). It also includes the money costs, opportunity costs, energy costs and psychic costs (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971). Focusing on just the price limits the success of behavioural change campaigns and could lead to "marketing myopia" (Lefebvre 2011, p. 62). The price for accepting and maintaining a good behaviour is as important (or even more important) as the economic price of obtaining a product or service in the traditional marketing setting. People may be reluctant to go for a safer driving campaign programme if it will rob them of their time to pursue their normal businesses (opportunity cost), demand them to make financial

contribution to the campaign (money costs), or not being recognised in the society for adopting a safer driving behaviour (social cost), etcetera.

Social marketing hopes to influence change for good and it is considered a success when both the social marketer and the customer are satisfied with the outcome of the programme (Brisibe, Ordinioha & Gbeneol, 2015). Thus, there is a special need for social marketers to develop programs that simultaneously consider cost and benefits for products and services that lead to better social behaviour (Lefebvre, 2011). These programs would be effective if they try to increase the benefits relative to the costs, or decrease the costs relative to the benefits, or have some mixture of product, place, promotion, and price that simultaneously increase the benefits and reduce the costs (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971).

Although it may be a challenging task, safer driving campaigns may be channelled in such a way that reduce the cost and barriers of participation and create incentives that further prompt behavioural change toward safer driving. People may be motivated to participate in behavioural change if they were given (or if they knew they would be given) incentives. Incentives, which is part of the price the customer in social marketing considers in making his decision to exchange, is a very important feature of the social marketing programme (Lefebvre & Flora, 1988). Incentives can either be real or perceived, tangible or intangible, financial or social, etcetera (Lefebvre & Flora, 1988). For a safer driving campaign in Nigeria, incentive could be in the form of gift, recognition, reduction in social/utility bills, scholarships to safer driving customers or to their wards to further their education or those of their children, etcetera. Remarkable success has been achieved in the polio eradication programme in Nigeria with the help and utilisation of different incentive offerings. Incentives in the form of consumables, treated mosquito nets, etcetera, were offered and these have contributed immensely to persuading the parents to offer their children for the polio immunisation programme. Social marketers in the safer driving campaign could borrow most of the ideas used in the polio immunisation programme in designing effective safer driving campaigns in the country.

A monitoring system may be created whose main aim is to monitor road traffic and reward motorists that exhibit a high sense of safety. Inter school contest or public debate system may be instituted to reward motorists who have shown the highest level of knowledge of road traffic rules, signs and regulations. This is because knowing the road traffic signs, rule and regulations and abiding by them is an important step forward toward safer highways. Different campaigns for different classes of people within the society may be relevant. This is because road traffic campaigns for older people may be different from those channelled to younger population.

People do not immediately change their behaviours upon subjected to change messages but the change passes through some series of steps, very quickly for some, slowly for some and gradually for others. This process begins with pre-contemplation (not really considering making the change); continues with contemplation of making the change, preparation (intention to make the change), action (making the change); and finally, ends with maintenance of the new behaviour (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). At every stage of the change agenda, social marketers need to design specific and often separate change programmes for a meaningful exchange to be observed. Late adopters of the programmes may be treated separately with early adopters.

3.1.3 Place: Just like the traditional marketing view, place plays an important role in the success of social marketing campaign. People may be limited in some ways to adopt life changing behaviours if they could not be able to do them, even if they actually want to do them. The social marketer must create access and opportunity for the people to try, practice, perform and sustain better behavioural alternatives and avoid unhealthy ones. The family planning campaign strategy that aimed at stimulating the practice of family planning in the 1960s in India projected the usage of some 400,000 selected retail outlets (200,000 each in the urban and the rural India) for the distribution of contraceptive condoms to families across the country (Chandy et al., 1965). This would include dry grocers (*Kiranas*), village shops, chemists (drug stores), cigarette sellers, general merchants, consumer cooperatives, tea stalls, etc. (Chandy et al., 1965). The aim of this practice was to make condom a normal household staple for many families that patronise these outlets (Chandy et al., 1965). Condoms were made available free of charge at government's designated outlets.

The United Nations Family Planning Association estimates that at least 200 million women around the globe would like to use safe and effective planning methods but could not be able to do so because they do not have access to information and services that support the application of these methods (Lee & Kotler, 2009). Place plays an important role in the achievement of any safer driving campaign in Nigeria. Motorists in Nigerian roads could be limited in some cases to adopt safer driving behaviours if there was no specific place to buy the products. Designated centres where people can get information about safer driving should be established. Special classes on safer driving in schools and universities where students and the public would be educated on better driving behaviour should be introduced. Good roads free of pot holes should be constructed and the existing ones adequately repaired. Speed limit devices should be made available and affordable to motorists. Safer road counselling sessions should be introduced in places known to have mass turnout of people. For example, a pre-consulting session that provides a discussion forum on the good side of safer driving to educate patients who visit the hospitals before they meet with the doctor or physician may be introduced.

This kind of initiative may be extended to schools, places of worship and places of work. The idea here is to bring the safer driving products closer to the people and to motivate them to perform their part of the job of getting rid of RTAs on Nigerian roads.

3.1.4 Promotion: Promotion is "the communication-persuasion strategy and tactics that will make the product familiar, acceptable, and even desirable to the audience" (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971 p. 7). According to Lefebvre (2011), promotion (communication) needs to work in conjunction with the other 3Ps of marketing in an integrated manner in order to create and increase acceptance for better behavioural changes among individual and the society. Just like the traditional marketing system, decisions on promotion for safer driving must be made in alliance with the objectives of the promotion. The objectives of the promotion should identify the target audience, how the target audience is going to be reached, the frequency of meetings with the target audience, the duration the promotion will last and the kind of behavioural effect expected of the entire program. According to Kotler (1975), cited in Lefebvre & Flora (1988 p. 308), "advertising, publicity, personal contact, and attention to creating an environment designed to produce specific cognitive and/or emotional effects on the target group (atmospherics) are specific ways by which promotion goals can be met."

Different communication channels could be used to persuade motorists to accept a safer driving campaign in Nigeria. Massive radio and television programmes, billboard messages, community or market shows could be very effective in bringing the safer driving product to the knowledge of the customers. As Nigerians attach high premium to their belief, religious organisations (especially mosques and churches) could be used to spread the message of safer driving. Cleric and religious leaders should be encouraged to include, as part of their routine activities, programmes that encourage behavioural change to a safer driving habit.

All these promotional campaigns should not be ad-hoc, but be continuous until the desired result is achieved. As mentioned earlier, social marketers in the safer driving campaigns, in conjunction with community, religious, and traditional leaders should organise public enlightenment campaigns on the benefits of safer driving and the bad side of it in schools, markets, places of worships, clubs, and any other place(s) that has the potential of attracting mass turn out of people. Safer driving education campaigns should be launched at local, regional and national levels. And to give it country-wide coverage and increase nation-wide acceptability, these forms of campaigns should be launched by political heads (local government chairman at the local level, governor at the state/regional level, and the President at the national level) at the various levels of government. Progress should be periodically monitored in order to build on successes recorded and remedy any challenge(s) confronting the progress of the programme.

The family planning campaign in India wished to change the furtive practice of selling the ideas of family planning but be made open and public whereby contraceptive condoms would become displayed and sold openly. Family planning posters and literature, and stockist signs were to become widely available in stores, bazaras and retail stores (Chandy et al., 1965). This was aimed at inducing the idea of family planning and increase the usage of condoms (Chandy et al., 1965). Thus, if used properly, promotion is a very important tool to market safer driving products and services and to make them more acceptable to the public, and enhance their utilisation.

IV. Conclusion

Road traffic accidents have become global issues that continue to challenge the world's social and economic development. An estimated 1.3 million people die to road traffic crashes every year. RTAs have become a leading cause of deaths for young, energetic and working class population aged 15-29 years. In Nigeria, analysis of the road transport crashes from 1960 to 2016 revealed that a total of 1,125,377 cases involving 1,559,851 persons were recorded, with 350,961 deaths and 1,208,890 injuries over the period under review. One study estimates that 29.1 percent of those involved in accidents suffer permanent disability while 13.5 percent are unable to return to work. The United Nations has in 2011 proclaimed a Decade of Action for Road Safety with a view to galvanising global support for actions to combat RTAs. However, it is now two years to the end of this initiative and RTAs have continue to shackle the necks of especially low and middle income countries. It is on this backdrop we present this study to illustrate that social marketing, if properly utilised, could be an effective remedy for persistent RTAs in a developing country like Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Adeyemi, O. A., & Adewole, D. A. (2017). Risk factors of road traffic accidents (rtas) among commercial interstate drivers in lagos state, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Medical Research*, 17(5), 20-26
- [2.] Akpoghomeh, O. S. (2012). The terror of transport and the transportation of terror. An inaugural lecture series no. 94, 27 September 2012, The University Of Port Harcourt
- [3.] Akpoghomeh, O. S. (2011). Exacerbating Factors and Actual Causes of traffic Accidents. Paper delivered at FRSC Regional Conference Port Harcourt 2011.

- [4.] AMO, T.(2014). The influences of drivers/riders in road traffic crashes in Ghana between 2001 and 2011. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 6(4), 49-56. doi:10.5539/gjhs.v6n4p49
- [5.] Ansari, S., Akhdar, F., Mandoorah, M. & Moutaery, K.(2000). Causes and effects of road traffic Accidents in Saudi Arabia. *Public Health*, 114(1), 37-39
- [6.] Arthur, N.(2015). A survey of commercial drivers' perception on the causes of road traffic accidents in Nigeria. *Journal of Medicine in the Tropics*, 17(1), 15-18. doi:10.4103/2276-7096.148563
- [7.] Asogwa, S., E.(1992). Road traffic accidents in Nigeria: a review and a reappraisal. *Accident Analysis and Preview*, 24(2), 149-155
- [8.] Asogwa, S., E. (1978). The age and sex distribution of casualties involved in various forms of road transportation in Nigeria. *Journal of Traffic Medicine*, 6(2), 27-30
- [9.] Atubi, A. O., & Gbadamosi, K., T.(2015). Global positioning and socio-economic impact of road traffic accidents in Nigeria: matters arising. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, (5)5, 136-146
- [10.] Banfi, S., Doll, C., Maibach, M., Rothengatter, W., Schenkel, P., Sieber, N., & Zuber, J.(2000). External costs of transport: Accident, environmental and congestion costs of transport in Western Europe. Zürich/Karlsruhe: INFRAS/IWW, University of Karlsruhe, University of Karlsruhe. Retrieved from <http://www.infras.ch/e/projekte/displayprojectitem.php?id=6>
- [11.] Bonča, S, Udovč, A. & Rodela, R. (2017). A social marketing perspective on road freight transportation of fresh fruits and vegetables: a Slovene case. *Economic Research*, 30(1), 1132-1151
- [12.] Bongardt, D, Schmid, D, Huizenga, C. & Litman, T. (2011). Sustainable Transport Evaluation Developing Practical Tools for Evaluation in the Context of the CSD Process. *Partnership on Sustainable Low carbon Transport (SLoCaT Partnership)*, Eschborn, Germany.
- [13.] Brisibe, S. F, Ordinioha, B. & Gbeneol, P. K.(2015). Framework for the social marketing of clinical preventive services in Nigeria. *World Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 3(1), 11-16. DOI:10.12691/jpm-3-1-3
- [14.] Chandy, K. T., Balakrishman, T. R., Kantawalla, J. M., Mohan, K., Sen, N. P., Gupta, S. S., & Srivastva, S., (1965). Proposals for family planning promotion: a marketing plan. *Studies in Family Planning*,1(6), 7-12
- [15.] European Commission, (2012). EU transport in figures: Statistical pocketbook 2012. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Retrieved from <http://ec.europa.eu/transport/factsfundings/statistics/doc/2012/pocketbook2012.pdf>
- [16.] Federal Road Safety Commission, (2016). *2016 frsc annual report*. Federal Road Safety Commission, Abuja, Nigeria
- [17.] Hastings, G., B. & Haywood, A. J., (1994). Social marketing: A critical response. *Health Promotion International*,9(1), 59-63
- [18.] Hastings, G., B. & Haywood, A., J.(1991). Social marketing and communication in health promotion. *Health Promotion International*, 6(2), 135-145.
- [19.] Kotler, P. & Zaltman, G.(1971). Social marketing: an approach to planned social change. *Journal of Marketing*, 35(July 1971), 3-12
- [20.] Labinjo, M, Jullrard, C, Kobusingye, O. C. & Hyder, A. A.(2010). Socio-economic impact of road traffic injuries in west Africa: exploratory data from Nigeria. *Injury Prevention*, 16, 389-392
- [21.] Lee, N, R. & Kotler, P.(2009). Ending poverty: what's social marketing got to do with it? *Social Marketing Quarterly*, 15(4), 134-140. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15245000903382508>
- [22.] Lefebvre, R., C.(2011).An integrative model for social marketing. *Journal of Social Marketing*, vol. 1(1) pp. 54 - 72
- [23.] Lefebvre, R., C. &Flora, J., A.(1988). Social marketing and public health intervention. *Health Education Quarterly*, 15, 299-315.
- [24.] Maibach, E.(1993). Social marketing for the environment: using information campaigns to promote environmental awareness and behavior change. *Health Promotion International*, 8, 209-224
- [25.] MCGovern, E. (2005). Social marketing applications and transportation demand management: an information instrument for the 21st century. *Journal of Public Transportation*, 8(5), 1-24
- [26.] Palamuleni, L. G., & David, B., O. (2015). Characterization of Road Traffic Accidents and Identification of Hotspots in a Typical Administrative City of Nigeria. *Ife Social Sciences Review*, 24(2), 96-108
- [27.] Perreault, W. D.,& McCarthy, E., J.(2002). *Basic marketing: a global-managerial approach*. 14 ed, McGraw-Hill Irwin, New York.
- [28.] Prochaska, J. O.& Velicer, W., F.(1997). The transtheoretical model of health behaviour change. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 12, 38-48
- [29.] ROSS, J., & TOMLINSON, B.(2011). Negabehaviors and environmental sustainability. *Journal of Sustainability Education*, 2 (March), 1-13.

- [30.] Smith, W., A.(2006). Social marketing: an overview of approach and effects. *Injury Prevention*,12, i38-i43
- [31.] United Nations, (2016). *Resolution adopted by the general assembly on 15 April 2016: 70/260 improving global road safety*. United Nations General Assembly, Seventieth Session, agenda item 13, A/RES/70/260.
- [32.] United Nations,(2012). *Resolution adopted by the general assembly: 66/260 improving global road safety*, A/RES/66/260. General Assembly. 23 May 2012
- [33.] United Nations, (2010). *Resolution adopted by the general assembly: 64/255 improving global road safety*, A/RES/64/255. General Assembly. 10 May 2010
- [34.] United Nations, (2009). *Moscow Declaration: First Global Ministerial Conference on Road Safety: Time for Action*, Moscow, 19-20 November 2009
- [35.] World Health Organisation, (2016b). *Addressing the challenges of the united nations decade of action for road safety (2011-2020): outcome of the second global high-level conference on road safety - time for results*. Sixty-ninth world health assembly, Agenda item 12.7, WHA69.7, 28 May 2016
- [36.] World Health Organisation,(2016c). *Post-crash response: supporting those affected by road traffic crashes*. Geneva, World Health Organisation
- [37.] World Health Organisation,(2015). *Global status report on road safety 2015*. Geneva, Switzerland, World Health Organization, 2015.
- [38.] World Health Organisation,(2011). *Decade of action for road safety 2011–2020: saving millions of lives*. World Health Organisation, Geneva